

Collaboration in crowdsourcing contests

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Crowdsourcing contests, specifically idea and design contests, are an important instrument for organizations to gather external ideas from the crowd (Schemmann et al., 2016). As these contests predominately take place in a virtual environment, they represent a specific type of idea generation or ideation (Paulus & Brown, 2007). According to Geiger et al. (2011), crowdsourcers can actively manage the electronic crowd ideation process by adjusting four design dimensions, namely *preselection of contributors*, *aggregation of contributions*, *renumeration of contributions* as well as the *accessibility of peer contribution*, i.e., the way participants are able to interact with each other or not. While the authors postulate that the latter is of lesser importance compared to the other design elements, traditional research in ideation and crowdsourcing evaluation indicates that interaction plays a crucial role in the quality of the outcome (Geiger, et al., 2011). In fact, various theories can be found in ideation literature, which show a rather disparate picture:

On the one hand, theories such as wisdom of the crowd and nominal groups suggest that interaction in ideation implies productivity losses such as production blocking as well as coordination problems, social loafing and increased vulnerability to cognitive biases and errors and thus, generates fewer ideas (Surowiecki, 2004; Paulus & Brown, 2007; Rietzschel, Nijstad & Stroebe, 2010). On the other hand, literature on bounded ideation, brainstorming and interactive groups puts emphasis on the productivity gains that come with interaction such as increased cognitive stimulation (Osborn, 1957; Briggs & Reinig, 2010). This stimulation can trigger the transition to other, more remote topic categories, increasing the diversity of ideas (Rietzschel, Nijstad & Stroebe, 2010).

In the context of crowdsourcing, several studies show that the configuration of the interaction element is not trivial. For example, research has shown that the best crowdsourcing ideas are posted in the second half of the contest and usually combine concepts of previously posted ideas, implying that knowledge integration through access of peer contributions is crucial for the outcome (Walter & Back, 2013). Furthermore, in recent years, interaction has been shown to be a predictor of good ideas and researchers have started to conceptualized collaboration process designs for crowdsourcing environments (Funke-Braun, 2013; Tavanapour & Bittner, 2017). Following these arguments, we postulate that interaction in crowdsourcing contests has an impact on contest idea quality and aim to answer the following question:

How do collaboration processes in crowdsourcing contests affect the total idea quality?

The emergence of rather underrepresented machine-learning based methodological approaches in innovation management research open up the possibility to analyze not only the volume of crowdsourcees' interactions but their structure and semantics (valence dimension), which we believe to have an influence on contest idea quality and its different dimensions.

With this research, we seek to up the black box of crowdsourcing processes and offer managers the possibility to identify weaknesses in interaction patterns, manage the creation of crowdsourced ideas and thus, optimize its performance. Furthermore, we aim to contribute to ideation literature and electronic group-based ideation in particular by identifying structural and semantic patterns and particularities, which positively influence idea quality in crowdsourcing contests.

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